

Adverse soils tolerance

Sensitivity of rice seedlings to salinity

M. Akhar and D. Senadhira, IRRI

We experimented to determine the age at which rice seedlings are most sensitive to salinity, using salt-tolerant varieties Nona Bokra and Pokkali and salt-sensitive IR28 and IR2035-117-3.

Pregerminated seeds were sown on Styrofoam sheets, each with 60 holes and a nylon net bottom, at one seed/hole, 60 seeds/variety. The sheets were floated in 40- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays filled with 9 liters nutrient solution N maintained at pH 5.0. Seedlings were grown at 29/21 °C (day/night) with about 70% relative humidity in the phytotron glasshouse under natural daylight.

Salinity stress of 6,800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) was introduced by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution at 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 d after seeding. Unsalinized trays of each variety were the checks. Seedling survival was measured 14 d after salinization.

Survival of unsalinized checks of all

varieties was 100%. Salt-tolerant Nona Bokra and Pokkali were not affected by salinity (see table). Seedlings of sensitive variety IR28 were severely affected up to 7 d, then gradually gained tolerance. IR2035-117-3 seedlings showed sensitivity up to 6 d. Varietal differences in salt sensitivity were apparent. Tolerance in sensitive varieties increased with age, showing that seedling age is a critical factor in screening for salt tolerance. □

Rice seedling survival after 14 d salinization (EC = 12 dS/m) pressure applied at different seedling ages. IRRI, 1988.

Variety	Survival (%) at each seedling age (d)									
	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Nona Bokra	100	100	100	98	96	100	100	100	100	100
Pokkali	82	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
IR28	2	17	12	20	70	70	97	100	100	100
IR2035-117-3	10	52	57	85	93	92	98	100	100	100

Performance of some acid tolerant rice varieties in two acid saline soils of Sunderbans

A. K. Bandyopadhyay, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Regional Research Station Canning, Canning Town, 24-Parganas(S), West Bengal, Pin: 743329 India

Grain yield of promising acid tolerant rice varieties. Sunderbans, India, 1987.

Variety, line	Grain yield (g/plant)	
	Nirdeshkhali	Belakhali
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	8.9	14.0
RD15	8.1	20.8
S4	6.9	8.3
Gablak - Cablal	6.9	7.4
IET230	6.9	8.6
S3	6.7	8.6
IR8067-41-IE-P1	6.7	12.2
BW100	6.7	10.8
Quisidugo	6.0	5.8
B2443B-KN-10-1-1-1	5.9	11.4
B221496-pn-26-1-1	5.5	12.3
SR26B	5.5	14.8
S5	5.5	13.5
S1	5.5	12.6
Jaca	5.5	10.1
ITA-116	5.5	5.0

We transplanted 51 promising acid tolerant rice varieties and lines collected from Indonesia, West Africa, Thailand, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, Philippines, India, and IRRI in acid saline soils of Nirdeshkhali (ECe 9.3-5.4 dS/m and pH 3.3-3.8) and Belakhali (ECe 4.0-3.0

dS/m, pH 5.0-5.8).

In the highly acid saline soils of Nirdeshkhali, the highest grain yields were from IR28222-9-2-2-2-2, and RD15 (see table). In less acidic conditions, RD15 gave the highest yield, followed by SR26B and IR28222-9-2-2-2-2. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

ADT39, a new rice variety for Tamil Nadu

P. Parthasarathy, R. Vaithilingam, W. W. Manuel, S. Vairavan, N. Nadarajan, V. Sivasubramanian, and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai, India

ADT39 is a derivative of IR8/IR20 made in 1976. It is a nonlodging semidwarf with 120- to 125-d duration and medium slender white rice.

Good grain yields were recorded in research station, All India Coordinated

Yield of ADT39 in Tamil Nadu, India.

Test	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)
	ADT39	IR20	
TRRI, Aduthurai	4.8	4.1	17
AICRIP trials (wet season)	3.8	3.3 ^a	15
AICRIP trials (dry season)	5.1	4.5 ^a	13
Adaptive research trials (Thanjavur district)	5.6	4.9	14
Crop cutting experiments (Thanjavur district)	6.3	4.5	40

^aJaya.